

PULSE: Real-Time Monitoring and Analysis Framework Leveraging Twitter Data

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Introduction

- Surveys has been a mode of data collection for decision making
- Survey research and its legitimacy to randomize samples
- The era of social media
- Twitter (currently X), its API's and data analytics

Motivation

- Even though techniques for data collection, processing and displaying results exist often they are not done real-time
- Same steps/processes need to be repeated for new data
- Results are not easily accessible over the web

PULSE

Real-time data ingestion platform which is capable of collecting real-time data from Twitter (currently X), analyzing the data, storing and displaying results on a web-based dashboard.

PULSE

PULSE

- Data collection and processing
 - Extraction of sentiment
 - Network Analysis
- Data Indexing and storage
- Visualization Dashboard

PULSE - Components

- Filters tab
- Tweet feed
- Time series
- Bar charts (hashtags, mentions, users, language etc.)
- Pie charts (tweet summary, sentiment, type of tweet)
- Network map
- World map
- Word cloud

PULSE - Flow

PULSE Projects Tweet Stream Servers Users Logout

List Create

Project Details

Name *

End Date

Keywords

Or upload a txt file with keywords in CSV format

Keywords File No file chosen

Location

[Generate Location Coordinates](#)

PULSE - Flow

List	Create	With selected▼	Search						
<input type="checkbox"/>			Id	Project	Stream Server	User	Tweets Count	Tweet Stream	Operations
<input type="checkbox"/>			37	work from home	Not Running	N/A	405638	Start	Delete Data
<input type="checkbox"/>			38	██████████	Not Running	N/A	10049638	Start	Delete Data
<input type="checkbox"/>			39	██████████	Not Running	N/A	58293	Start	Delete Data
<input type="checkbox"/>			42	██████████	Not Running	N/A	1355488	Start	Delete Data
<input type="checkbox"/>			43	██████████	Not Running	N/A	1861	Start	Delete Data
<input type="checkbox"/>			50	██████████	Not Running	N/A	5626560	Start	Delete Data
<input type="checkbox"/>			51	██████████	Twitter Stream Server 1	N/A		Stop	Delete Data

PULSE - Flow

- Create a project by providing name, keywords, location boundary etc.
- Start the project to collect data
- Once started
 - Data pod collects data from twitter
 - Analyze the tweets for sentiment and network map
 - Store the results in Elastic search
- Dashboard shows the collected tweet count and in-depth analysis

Case Study

- This case study has been conducted during Hurricane Laura to study the reaction over Twitter using the PULSE tool
- Nearly 1.8M tweets were captured during a short period of 26th August to 1st September 2020.

Case Study

Future Work

- Extend the tool to create a platform to consume data from variety of social media source (Facebook, Reddit, Instagram etc.), text files, databases
- Create customizable dashboards
- Integrate advanced data analysis models

Questions

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Thank You